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Review Article

**ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF
PATHOLOGY, EPIDEMIOLOGY, AND THERAPEUTIC
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411044 [M.S] India**1. Abstract:**

Alzheimer's disease (AD), the most common form of dementia, is characterized by neuritic plaques and neurofibrillary tangles resulting from the accumulation of amyloid-beta peptide in the brain. Since its first description by Alois Alzheimer in 1907, the disease has been associated with significant cognitive decline and loss of neurons. AD and other cerebral disorders can stem from various causes, including genetic factors, infections, cardiovascular issues, and more. With approximately 50 million AD patients worldwide, a number expected to triple by 2050, the disease imposes a substantial economic burden, with annual global costs estimated at \$1 trillion. This review provides an overview of AD pathology, diagnosis, causes, and current treatments. It explores the historical background, epidemiology, neuropathology, and pathophysiology of AD. The review also highlights emerging therapies targeting multiple pathogenic mechanisms, such as tau and A β aggregation, inflammation, and oxidative damage. By synthesizing current research and trends, this article aims to offer valuable insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers involved in addressing the challenges of Alzheimer's disease.

Keywords: Beta-amyloid plaques, Neurofibrillary tangles, Synaptic loss, Exercise intervention, Diagnosis and treatment

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2. INTRODUCTION:

The most common type of dementia is called Alzheimer's disease (AD), named for the German psychiatrist Alois Alzheimer. It is characterised by neuritic plaques and neurofibrillary tangles (Figure 1), which are caused by the accumulation of amyloid-beta peptide ($A\beta$) in the brain's most affected area, the medial temporal lobe, and neocortical structures [1]. When Alois Alzheimer examined the brain of his first patient, who experienced memory loss and a change in personality before to death, he found amyloid plaques and a tremendous loss of neurons. He classified the patient's condition as a terrible disease of the cerebral cortex [2,3].

Cerebral disorders such as Alzheimer's disease (AD) or other conditions like infections, intoxications, abnormalities in the pulmonary and circulatory systems, which reduce oxygen supply to the brain, malnutrition, vitamin B12 deficiency, tumours, and others can cause progressive loss of cognitive functions [4,5]. Currently, there are about 50 million AD patients globally; by 2050, that number is expected to have doubled every five years to 152 million. The burden of AD impacts people, their families, and the economy; the annual global costs are estimated to be \$1 trillion. Alzheimer's disease currently has no known cure, however there are therapies that can help with symptoms [6, 7]. This review aims to provide a concise overview of AD pathology, diagnosis, causes, and current treatments. It also highlights the development of new compounds that target multiple pathogenic mechanisms, including tau and $A\beta$ aggregation, misfolding, inflammation, oxidative damage, and others, and may be used to treat or prevent AD. The main aim of this review article is to study the historical background, pathophysiology, etiology, symptoms, diagnosis and treatment.

3. Historical Background:

The first case of Alzheimer's disease was described in 1907 by German physician Alois Alzheimer [8]. In 1901, he laid eyes on 51-year-old Auguste Deter for the first time. When Auguste started acting strangely, hiding things, threatening neighbours, and accusing her husband of adultery, her husband Karl took her to a psychiatric hospital. She also lost her capacity to perform housework and cooking, among other daily tasks. Auguste was admitted to a Frankfurt mental health facility for Alzheimer's treatment. He saw and noted her patterns of behaviour there: she could talk but not write her own name; she could name things like a pencil but not the meal she was eating; at times she was courteous but at other times rude and boisterous.

Auguste was diagnosed with "presenile dementia" by him [9].

Her brain had an Alzheimer's biopsy in 1906, which found "particular changes in cortical cell clusters" in addition to generalised cortical atrophy [10]. Alzheimer's disease was associated with plaques and tangles of nerve fibres that were later identified as tau neurofibrillary tangles and beta amyloid plaques by researchers in the 1980s [11,12]. When Alzheimer presented Auguste's case at a German psychiatric conference that year, he claimed that her symptoms stemmed from these cortical abnormalities. The following year, he released a research report, and in 1910, he dubbed the condition "Alzheimer's disease" in a psychiatric textbook.

In the United States, the clinical diagnostic standards for AD were standardised in 1984 [13]. They were updated in 2011 and 2018 to acknowledge the significance of biomarkers in AD diagnosis and to establish distinct diagnoses for the preclinical, moderate cognitive impairment (MCI), and dementia stages of the disease [14,15].

4. Epidemiology and Etiology:

The intricate and diverse pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease is still being investigated, but the genetic, environmental, and social factors that contribute to the development of this neurological deterioration have received a lot of attention. The primary risk factor for the development of Alzheimer's disease is thought to be ageing; only 1-6 percent of cases are early-onset AD (EOAD), which is defined as beginning between the ages of 30 and 65 (17). With a present frequency of about 6.5 million cases in the US and a projected increase to 13.8 million by 2065, late-onset AD (LOAD) is far more common (23). The annual incidence of LOAD in the US varies significantly by age group, which further illustrates the link between aging and AD: in 2011, the incidence was 3.2% for those 75–84 years old, 7.6% for those over 85 years old, and 0.4% for those 65–74 years old (17). Out of the 6.5 million cases that are now known to exist, over 4 million affect women yet only 2.5 million affect males (17). The reason for this disparity is not entirely obvious, but one important contributing element is that women typically live longer than men do. Furthermore, there are racial and ethnic differences in the frequency of Alzheimer's disease, with Black and Hispanic Americans having a far higher diagnosis rate than White Americans (17). It is challenging to pinpoint the exact cause of these differences, but research points to the combination of biological and structural elements that play a role in the social construction of race (18). It is impossible to overstate

the cumulative effects of systemic racism on health (19); social and environmental factors like exposure to toxins and pollutants, access to healthcare, and educational attainment have all contributed to a documented rise in conditions like depression, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease that change an individual's risk of AD (20).

Over 50 million people worldwide are thought to have Alzheimer's disease, and this number is expected to rise significantly (21); the main causes of this increase are population growth, rising average life expectancy, and advancements in the detection and diagnosis of the disease (particularly in less developed nations and underprivileged areas of the United States).

Regarding the correlation between ageing and Alzheimer's disease, numerous general characteristics of senescence, such as cognitive decline, metabolic deficiencies, and the formation of senile plaque/NFT, may potentially exacerbate the disease's pathology (22). Nevertheless, these factors also make it more difficult to develop biomarker-based diagnostic tests, as many molecular patterns linked to AD pathology may not always accurately reflect the illness, as is the case with A β plaque formation (23).

Presence of specific deterministic or predisposing genes is, by far, the most studied risk factor for AD development; in fact, studies indicate that the inheritability of AD is 50% or higher (24). Numerous such genes have been discovered to date through genome-wide association studies, many of which are directly related to the previously described amyloid theory. The amyloid precursor protein is encoded by APP, the first of them. As of 2020, this gene had 30 known mutations, 25 of which caused an increase in the synthesis of A β 42 and its accumulation due to modifications in the amino acid composition of the cleavage site of APP (16). The development of AD is also thought to be causally linked to mutations in the genes PSEN1 and PSEN2, whose protein products are important in activating the γ -secretase complex (25). The Apolipoprotein E (ApoE) gene's ϵ 4 allele, which is present in about 40% of AD patients, is the most significant genetic risk factor, nevertheless (26). The fact that DNA from HSV-1 infection—which is known to be a risk factor for AD—has been found in the brains of people who have the ApoE- ϵ 4 allele (27), demonstrates how risk factors can influence one another.

Other known variables that affect the likelihood of developing AD include intelligence and level of education attained; some argue that these attributes

may even lower the incidence of neural damage linked to AD, but the majority support a theory (the cognitive reserve hypothesis) that maintains cognitive function even in the presence of neural damage due to extensive early brain development (28). Beyond these, several lifestyle-related factors, including nutrition, exercise, prior brain injury, and cardiovascular health, have been statistically correlated with late-onset dementia (16); however, there is conflicting evidence regarding the relationship between these factors and particular Alzheimer's pathology, necessitating additional research. Nonetheless, compelling studies have been carried out regarding the contribution of stress to the pathophysiology of AD, particularly with the influence of corticotropin-releasing hormone signalling on the deposition of tau and A β , as well as neurodegeneration (29).

5. Prevalence:

Because Alzheimer's disease (AD) is becoming more common, especially in older populations, it represents a serious threat to world health. According to epidemiological research, the prevalence of AD is increasing, although estimates vary depending on the area and population. The Alzheimer's Association projects that 5.8 million Americans 65 and older will have Alzheimer's disease (AD) in 2020, and that figure will rise to over 14 million by 2050 (30). An estimated 50 million people worldwide are thought to have dementia, with AD accounting for a sizable share of cases (31). The frequency of AD doubles roughly every five years beyond the age of 65, making age the primary risk factor (32). Other factors that affect disease risk include genetic predisposition, lifestyle, and environmental factors. To support affected people and their families, there is an urgent need for effective prevention efforts, early diagnosis, and comprehensive treatment approaches. The rising prevalence of AD poses serious problems for healthcare systems and society globally. Our understanding of AD prevalence and risk factors has been enriched by a plethora of research and review papers, including those that are referenced. This underscores the significance of tackling this expanding public health concern through interdisciplinary initiatives.

6. Causes of Disease:

Between 60% and 70% of cases of dementia are caused by Alzheimer's disease. It is a long-term neurodegenerative illness that often begins slowly and deteriorates with time. According to one explanation, plaques prevent nerve cells in the brain from corresponding with one another. Tangles may impede the cells' ability to absorb the necessary nutrients. It makes sense that as Alzheimer's progresses, more and

more nerve cells—also referred to as neurons—die. This is how the disease progresses.

1. Age: The most important element in Alzheimer's disease development is age. After the age of 65, your chance of acquiring the disorder increases every five years.

2. Down syndrome: Alzheimer's disease is more likely to strike those who have Down syndrome. This is because the same genetic flaw that causes Down's syndrome can also accumulate amyloid plaques in the brain over time, which in certain cases can result in Alzheimer's disease.

3. Genetics: Based on analyses of twin and family studies, the genetic heritability of Alzheimer's disease (and its memory components) ranges from 49% to 79%. Familial types of autosomal (not sex-linked) dominant inheritance that begin before the age of 65 account for about 0.1% of instances. Early onset familial Alzheimer's disease is the term used to describe this type of the illness. Even though it's uncommon, just a tiny fraction of people has AD before turning 65. Presenilin 1 (PSEN1), Presenilin 2 (PSEN2), and amyloid precursor protein (APP) are the three genes that have been related to the development of AD through mutation (33).

- Late onset Alzheimer's gene- Apolipoprotein E is the gene linked to AD, which often appears after the age of 65 (APOE). There are three types of APOE, and APOE e4 one raises the risk of Alzheimer's. Additional genes linked to AD include CR1, PICALM, CLU, SORL1, and so on (33). The majority of autosomal dominant familial AD is caused by mutations in one of three genes: presenilins 1 and 2 and which encode the protein known as amyloid precursor protein (APP).

- APP amyloid beta precursor protein- The gene in doubt encodes a transmembrane precursor protein and a cell surface receptor. These proteins are cleaved by secretases into a variety of peptides, which upon secretion bind to the acetyltransferase complex APBB1/TIP60 to facilitate transcriptional activation and serve as the protein foundation for the amyloid plaques that are discovered in the brains of Alzheimer's disease patients. Chromosome 21 contains this gene. The pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease is linked to the constitutive increase of soluble β -amyloids, which in turn causes the formation of amyloid plaques. The monoclonal antibodies solanezumab, crenezumab, and gantenerumab, which target soluble and insoluble A β -aggregates, are part of the anti-amyloid therapy; however, because of their limitations and side effects,

they were unable to improve the clinical results of AD (34,35).

- APOE apolipoprotein E- The protein that this gene encodes is required for the proper degradation of components of lipoproteins that are high in triglycerides. It binds to a particular liver and peripheral cell receptor. This gene is located on chromosome 19, together with the genes for apolipoprotein C1 and C2. Type III hyperlipoproteinemia (HLP III), which is caused by mutations in this gene, is characterised by elevated plasma cholesterol and triglycerides because of decreased clearance of chylomicron and VLDL remnants.

Most mutations in the presenilin and APP genes promote the formation of A β 42, a tiny protein that is the primary constituent of senile plaques. Certain mutations only modify the proportion of A β 42 to the other major forms, specifically A β 40, without elevating the levels of A β 42. This implies that presenilin mutations may contribute to disease even in cases where they reduce the total amount of A β generated. Additionally, it may indicate other functions for presenilin or changes in the way that APP and/or its fragments work in addition to producing A β . There are protective variations of the APP gene. When they are mutated, large amounts of the dangerous protein fragment known as amyloid-beta peptide are produced. Tau protein fails as these fragments clump together and build up as amyloid plaques in the brain. The brain cells die, and the symptoms of Alzheimer's disease appear as the tau protein particles clump together to create neurofibrillary tangles (33).

7. Neuropathology:

Neuropathological alterations in AD are classified into two categories: 1] positive lesions (due to accumulation), which are defined by the build-up of neurofibrillary tangles, amyloid plaques, dystrophic neurites, neuropil threads, and other deposits in the brains of AD patients. These changes offer insight into the course of the disease and its symptoms. Furthermore, there are 2] negative lesions (caused by losses) that exhibit significant atrophy because of a loss of neurons, neuropils, and synapses. In addition, oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and damage to cholinergic neurons can all contribute to neurodegeneration (36,37,38).

7.1. Senile Plaques (SP) -

Beta-amyloid protein (A β) extracellular deposits, known as senile plaques, can take on several morphological forms, such as neuritic, diffuse, dense-core, classic, or compact type plaques. The

transmembrane amyloid precursor protein (APP) is the source of A β deposits, which are produced by proteolytic cleavage enzymes such β - and γ -secretase (39,40, 41). These enzymes break down APP into fragments of amino acids 43, 45, 46, 48, 49, and 51, which combine to generate the final forms of A β 40 and A β 42. A β monomers come in many forms: soluble oligomers that can proliferate throughout the brain and massive, insoluble amyloid fibrils that can build up to create amyloid plaques. Because A β is involved in neurotoxicity and neural function, the build-up of denser plaques in the cerebral cortex, amygdala, and hippocampus can result in cognitive impairments as well as damage to axons, dendrites, and loss of synapses, as well as stimulation of astrocytes and microglia (41,42,43).

7.2. Neurofibrillary Tangles (NFTs) -

NFT are aberrant filaments of hyperphosphorylated tau protein that can, at certain phases, coil around one another to form paired helical filaments (PHF). These filaments build up in the cytoplasm of neuralperikaryal axons, dendrites, and cytoplasm of neuralperikaryal cytoplasm, which results in the loss of tubulin-associated proteins and cytoskeletal microtubules. The primary component of NFTs in the brains of AD patients is hyperphosphorylated tau protein, and the evolution of this protein can indicate the morphological phases of NFTs, which include: 1] the extracellular tangles, also known as the ghost NFTs stage, which arises from a neuronal loss caused by large amounts of filamentous tau protein with partial resistance to proteolysis; 2] the pre-tangle phase, one type of NFT, where phosphorylated tau proteins are accumulated in the somatodendritic compartment without the formation of PHF; and 3] mature NFTs, which are characterised by filament aggregation of tau protein with the displacement of the nucleus to the periphery part of the soma (44,45).

7.3. Synaptic Loss -

Memory impairment results from synaptic loss in the neocortex and limbic system, which is typically seen in the early stages of AD. Defects in axonal transport, oxidative stress, mitochondrial damage, and other processes that might lead to small fractions, such as the accumulation of tau and A β at the synaptic sites, are examples of synaptic loss mechanisms. Pre-synaptic terminals, axonal degeneration, and dendritic spine loss are the results of these processes (46). Visinin-like protein-1 (VILIP-1), neurogranin, a postsynaptic neuronal protein, and synaptotagmin-1 are examples of synaptic proteins that function as biomarkers for the detection of synaptic loss and severity (47,48).

8. Pathophysiology:

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a complex neurological illness that is marked by behavioural abnormalities, memory loss, and progressive cognitive deterioration. AD has a complicated aetiology that is influenced by several interrelated processes in its pathophysiology. The accumulation of amyloid beta (A β) peptides, which create extracellular plaques in the brain parenchyma and impair synaptic function while fostering neurotoxicity, is one notable feature (49). Simultaneously, aberrant tau protein phosphorylation causes intracellular neurofibrillary tangles, which hinder axonal transit and worsen neuronal dysfunction (50). Additionally, neuroinflammation is crucial, as pro-inflammatory cytokines are released by activated microglia and astrocytes, aggravating the damage to neurons (51). As a result of cellular damage and mitochondrial malfunction brought on by an imbalance between reactive oxygen species and antioxidant defences, oxidative stress also plays a role in neurodegeneration (52). When the blood-brain barrier (BBB) is compromised, neurotoxic chemicals can more easily enter the brain, aggravating inflammation, and neuronal damage (54). Familial forms of AD are associated with genetic variables, indicating the genetic foundation of the disease. These factors include mutations in the presenilin 1 (PSEN1), presenilin 2 (PSEN2), and amyloid precursor protein (APP) genes (55). Neurotransmission and synaptic plasticity are hampered by early synaptic dysfunction, which precedes neuronal death and adds to cognitive decline (53). Clinical trials and disease monitoring are facilitated by biomarkers, such as tau levels and cerebrospinal fluid A β , which offer significant diagnostic and prognostic information (56). Numerous studies and review papers have provided a thorough understanding of AD pathogenesis, which highlights the disease's complexity and the pressing need for focused therapeutic strategies.

9. Symptoms:

A person's quality of life can be greatly impacted by the range of cognitive, functional, and behavioural symptoms that are the hallmark of Alzheimer's disease (AD), and these symptoms deteriorate over time. Early symptoms are frequently mild memory impairment, such forgetting appointments, or recent discussions, which progressively worsens to more severe memory problems, like trouble remembering familiar facts or identifying family members (57,58). As the illness progresses, patients may encounter difficulties with language, such as trouble following a conversation or coming up with the proper words, as well as deficits in executive functioning and spatial orientation, which

can make it harder to plan, solve problems, and make decisions (57,58). Apathy, depression, agitation, and irritability are among the usual behavioural changes that might worsen carer stress and burden (59,60). As motor function and coordination deteriorate in the later stages of AD, people may need assistance with everyday living activities like dressing, bathing, and using the restroom (57). Sundowning behaviours, roaming, and sleep difficulties might also happen, which makes managing and providing care more difficult (59,61). This complex symptom presentation highlights the variability of AD and the necessity of thorough care and assessment strategies to meet the various requirements of afflicted people and their families. Our understanding of AD symptomatology has been enriched by a plethora of research and review papers, some of which are referenced. These studies and publications emphasise the significance of early recognition, precise diagnosis, and customised therapies to enhance patient outcomes and carer support.

10. Diagnosis:

A thorough diagnostic procedure, comprising physical examinations, neurological testing, cognitive evaluations, and medical history evaluations, is usually required to diagnose Alzheimer's disease. To guide their evaluation, medical practitioners frequently depend on predefined diagnostic criteria (62,64). The assessment seeks to rule out additional conditions such as vitamin shortages, thyroid issues, or depression that may contribute to cognitive decline and dementia. Neuroimaging methods such as positron emission tomography (PET) scans and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can also be used to identify brain abnormalities typical of Alzheimer's disease, such as tau tangles and beta-amyloid plaques. Furthermore, biomarker tests—like the study of cerebrospinal fluid—can offer insightful information about the disease's underlying pathophysiology (63).

11. Treatment:

There is yet no proven treatment for Alzheimer's disease, a neurological condition that progresses over time. Nonetheless, a few therapies try to control symptoms and halt the disease's advancement. Cholinesterase inhibitors, such as galantamine, rivastigmine, and donepezil, raise acetylcholine levels in the brain to help with cognitive performance and symptom management (65). This is one of the main pharmaceutical methods. Memantine and other NMDA receptor antagonists are a class of medications that control glutamate activity to support the maintenance of cognitive function (66). Furthermore, lifestyle modifications including consistent exercise,

mental stimulation, and an antioxidant-rich diet may help manage symptoms and enhance quality of life for Alzheimer's patients (67). With the goal of creating more potent medications or perhaps a cure in the future, ongoing research is still investigating possible medicines that target the tau and amyloid-beta proteins in addition to immunotherapies, gene therapies, and stem cell treatments (68).

12. Exercise as Treatment for AD:

Although numerous studies show that exercise can potentially slow down cognitive deterioration, what proof is there that exercise can help those with Alzheimer's disease? Prior research has shown some difficulties concerning treatment group monitoring and randomization. Additionally, there aren't as much extensive research that focus on an Alzheimer's patient population.

An exercise program's potential to lessen the deterioration in ADLs among nursing home patients with AD was examined in a randomised, controlled experiment (69) to address some of these problems. They observed a slower reduction in ADL than in the non-exercise groups after a year of aerobic, strength, balance, and flexibility training for one hour twice a week. Regrettably, they discovered no difference in nutritional ratings, sadness, or behavioural abnormalities.

Strohle et al. (70) tried in 2015 to contrast the benefits of exercise with the effects of medicine for AD and MCI. The studies that were approved for inclusion included either a pharmaceutical intervention or exercise as a treatment arm. For AD, exercise showed a moderate to large, pooled effect size, but for MCI, the benefits were smaller. Memantine and cholinesterase inhibitors have little effect on cognition in AD patients and no effect in MCI patients. It should be mentioned that while the rate of medication discontinuation was very high, it was significantly lower for the exercise groups.

The benefits of a moderate-to-high intensity aerobic exercise programme on patients with mild AD were examined in a recent randomised controlled experiment (71). While there were no improvements in cognitive performance after 16 weeks of three times a week, there was a significant improvement in the scores related to neuropsychiatric symptoms. There were problems with the subjects' adherence to the training regimen in this study. Because of this frequent problem, most of this research employ intent to treat models.

The likelihood that compliance may deteriorate over the course of a study increases with the length of the intervention. This raises concerns about how long an intervention must last to produce a change. Three times a week, a supervised exercise programme was the subject of a randomised research that lasted only three months (72). They discovered that during the training phase, both immediate and delayed memory improved. Additionally, the anterior cingulate region showed increased cerebral blood flow at rest in the exercise group. Since all these subjects were adults with typical cognitive abilities, it is challenging to extrapolate these findings to individuals with AD. The tiny sample size [37 participants] and lack of follow-up in this study were other drawbacks. Another small trial examined a 9-month intervention with two 3-month training periods (73) and involved eight persons with MCI. Their cognitive performance improved, but once the training was stopped, the effect subsided.

The impact of exercise on elderly individuals with dementia was investigated in a recent Cochrane study (74). Their meta-analysis did not find any conclusive proof that exercise improves cognitive performance. They did discover, nonetheless, that exercise improved the subjects' capacity to carry out ADLs. It should be noted that the reviewers gave the evidence a very poor-quality rating due to their finding that the studies and outcomes were inconsistent. They suggested that additional carefully planned trials evaluating various forms and degrees of dementia might be beneficial in raising the standard of subsequent evaluations (74).

Finally, six randomised controlled studies that showed a favourable benefit in patients with AD who undertook an exercise programme were discovered by another recent systematic review with an associated meta-analysis (75). They showed improvement in overall cognitive function and a slowed pace of cognitive decline.

13. Challenges and Future Directions:

Alzheimer's patients and carers face several obstacles because of the condition, which calls for creative management and treatment strategies. The difficulty of diagnosis is one of the difficulties since early detection is still difficult to achieve even with advances in biomarker research (76). Furthermore, the disease's progressive nature makes it difficult to implement meaningful interventions, as present therapies mainly address symptoms rather than changing the course of the illness (77). Another urgent problem is carer burden, which frequently overwhelms families due to its financial, physical, and emotional demands (78). Furthermore, the difficulties marginalised people

confront are made worse by differences in access to care and assistance (79).

To overcome these obstacles, precision medicine strategies that are customised to each patient's unique genetic and environmental risk factors will be the focus of future Alzheimer's research (80). Modifying the disease may be possible with novel medicines that target the underlying pathophysiology, such as tau protein accumulation and amyloid-beta accumulation (81). Moreover, incorporating technology-based solutions could improve early detection and tailored treatment administration, such as digital therapies and remote monitoring (82). The advancement of knowledge and care of Alzheimer's disease will ultimately improve outcomes for both patients and carers, therefore cross-sector collaboration will be essential.

14. CONCLUSION:

The extensive study of Alzheimer's disease (AD) has shown that this neurological condition presents a major global health concern with wide-ranging social, economic, and individual consequences. We have gained important insights into the multifaceted character of AD through the historical framework provided by Alois Alzheimer's original observations to the current understanding of its complicated neuropathology, epidemiology, and aetiology.

Ageing populations, genetic predispositions, and environmental variables are the main causes of the rising prevalence of AD. Effective preventative measures, prompt diagnosis, and all-encompassing treatment options continue to be elusive despite scientific advancements. The current paradigm of care emphasises symptom management over stopping or reversing the course of the disease, highlighting the critical need for novel therapeutic approaches.

The neuropathological features of Alzheimer's disease (AD) include senile plaques, neurofibrillary tangles, and synaptic loss. These features also contribute to the syndrome's cognitive, functional, and behavioural symptoms. Clinical assessment, MRI, and biomarker testing are all used in the diagnosis process, although early detection is still difficult.

Pharmacological treatments such as memantine and cholinesterase inhibitors provide symptomatic relief, but lifestyle changes and new research on innovative therapeutics such as gene and immunotherapies could lead to more effective treatment plans in the future.

Furthermore, the advantages of exercise in reducing

cognitive decline and enhancing neuropsychiatric symptoms underscore the significance of comprehensive strategies in the management of AD.

Significant obstacles still exist, though, such as the disease's degenerative nature, the stress placed on carers, and differences in access to care. Innovative research, interdisciplinary teamwork, and individualised treatment strategies are needed to meet these obstacles.

Promising developments in technology-based treatments and personalised medical programmes catered to specific genetic and environmental risk factors provide promise for better results for AD patients and their careers.

Conclusively, although Alzheimer's disease poses a significant obstacle, continuous investigations and cooperative endeavours promise to enhance our comprehension and handling of this intricate neurological condition, ultimately contributing to the betterment of the lives of those impacted by AD.

REFERENCES:

- De-Paula V.J., Radanovic M., Diniz B.S., Forlenza O.V. Alzheimer's disease. *Sub-Cell. Biochem.* 2012;65:329–352. doi: 10.1007/978-94-007-5416-4_14.
- Cipriani G., Dolciotti C., Picchi L., Bonuccelli U. Alzheimer and his disease: A brief history. *Neurol. Sci. Off. J. Ital. Neurol. Soc. Ital. Soc. Clin. Neurophysiol.* 2011;32:275–279. doi: 10.1007/s10072-010-0454-7.
- Blass J.P. Alzheimer's disease. *Dis. A Mon. Dm.* 1985;31:1–69. doi: 10.1016/0011-5029(85)90025-2.
- Terry R.D., Davies P. Dementia of the Alzheimer type. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.* 1980;3:77–95. doi: 10.1146/annurev.ne.03.030180.000453.
- Rathmann K.L., Conner C.S. Alzheimer's disease: Clinical features, pathogenesis, and treatment. *Drug Intell. Clin. Pharm.* 1984;18:684–691. doi: 10.1177/106002808401800902.
- Yiannopoulou K.G., Papageorgiou S.G. Current and future treatments in Alzheimer disease: An update. *J. Cent. Nerv. Syst. Dis.* 2020;12. doi: 10.1177/1179573520907397.
- Livingston G., Huntley J., Sommerlad A., Ames D., Ballard C., Banerjee S., Brayne C., Burns A., Cohen-Mansfield J., Cooper C., et al. Dementia prevention, intervention, and care: 2020 report of the Lancet Commission. *Lancet.* 2020;396:413–446. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30367-6.
- Alzheimer A. Uber eine eigenartige Erkrankung der Hirnrinde. *Zentralbl. Nervenhe. Psych.* 1907;18:177-9.
- Yang HD, Kim DH, Lee SB, Young LD. History of Alzheimer's Disease. *Dementia and Neurocognitive Disorders.* 2016 Dec 1;15(4):115-21.
- Soria Lopez JA, Gonzalez HM, and Leger GC. Chapter 13 – Alzheimer's disease. *Handbook of Clinical Neurology* 2019; 167: 231-255.
- Glenner GG, Wong CW. Alzheimer's disease: initial report of the purification and characterization of a novel cerebrovascular amyloid protein. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications.* 1984 May 16;120(3):885-90.
- Brion JP, Couck AM, Passareiro E, Flament-Durand J. Neurofibrillary tangles of Alzheimer's disease: an immunohistochemical study. *Journal of Submicroscopic Cytology.* 1985 Jan 1;17(1):89-96.
- McKhann G, Drachman D, Folstein M, Katzman R, Price D, Stadlan EM. Clinical diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease: Report of the NINCDS-ADRDA Work Group* under the auspices of Department of Health and Human Services Task Force on Alzheimer's Disease. *Neurology.* 1984 Jul 1;34(7):939-44.
- McKhann GM, Knopman DS, Chertkow H, Hyman BT, Jack Jr CR, Kawas CH, et al. The diagnosis of dementia due to Alzheimer's disease: recommendations from the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia.* 2011 May;7(3):263-9.
- Jack Jr CR, Bennett DA, Blennow K, Carrillo MC, Dunn B, Haeberlein SB, et al. NIA-AA research framework: toward a biological definition of Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia.* 2018 Apr;14(4):535-62.
- Breijyeh, Z, and Karaman, R. Comprehensive review on Alzheimer's disease: causes and treatment. *Molecules.* (2020) 25:3–9. doi: 10.3390/molecules25245789
- Alzheimer's Association. 2022 Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. *Alzheimers Dement.* (2022) 18:700–89. doi: 10.1002/alz.12638
- Barnes, LL. Alzheimer disease in African American individuals: increased incidence or not enough data? *Nat Rev Neurol.* (2022) 18:56–62. doi: 10.1038/s41582-021-00589-3
- Churchwell, K, Elkind, MSV, Benjamin, RM, Carson, AP, Chang, EK, Lawrence, W, et al. Call to action: structural racism as a fundamental driver of health disparities: a presidential advisory

- from the American Heart Association. *Circulation*. (2020) 142:e454–68. doi: 10.1161/CIR.0000000000000936
- 20.Dreeben, O. Health status of African Americans. *J Health Soc Policy*. (2001) 14:1–17. doi: 10.1300/J045v14n01_01
- 21.Li, X, Feng, X, Sun, X, Hou, N, Han, F, and Liu, Y. Global, regional, and national burden of Alzheimer's disease and other dementias, 1990–2019. *Front Aging Neurosci*. (2022) 14:937486. doi: 10.3389/fnagi.2022.937486
- 22.Liu, RM. Aging, cellular senescence, and Alzheimer's disease. *Int J Mol Sci*. (2022) 23:1989. doi: 10.3390/ijms23041989
- 23.Dickson, DW, Crystal, HA, Mattiace, LA, Masur, DM, Blau, AD, Davies, P, et al. Identification of normal and pathological aging in prospectively studied nondemented elderly humans. *Neurobiol Aging*. (1992) 13:179–89. doi: 10.1016/0197-4580(92)90027-u
- 24.Golde, TE. Alzheimer's disease—the journey of a healthy brain into organ failure. *Mol Neurodegener*. (2022) 17:2. doi: 10.1186/s13024-022-00523-1
- 25.De Strooper, B. Loss-of-function presenilin mutations in Alzheimer disease. Talking point on the role of presenilin mutations in Alzheimer disease. *EMBO Rep*. (2007) 8:141–6. doi: 10.1038/sj.embor.7400897
- 26.Farrer, LA, Cupples, LA, Haines, JL, Hyman, B, Kukull, WA, Mayeux, R, et al. Effects of age, sex, and ethnicity on the association between apolipoprotein E genotype and Alzheimer disease. A meta-analysis. APOE and Alzheimer disease Meta analysis consortium. *JAMA*. (1997) 278:1349–56. doi: 10.1001/jama.1997.03550160069041
- 27.Seaks, CE, and Wilcock, DM. Infectious hypothesis of Alzheimer disease. *PLoS Pathog*. (2020) 16:e1008596. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1008596
- 28.Yeo, RA, Arden, R, and Jung, RE. Alzheimer's disease and intelligence. *Curr Alzheimer Res*. (2011) 8:345–53. doi: 10.2174/1567205111795745276
- 29.Futch, HS, Croft, CL, Truong, VQ, Krause, EG, and Golde, TE. Targeting psychologic stress signaling pathways in Alzheimer's disease. *Mol Neurodegener*. (2017) 12. doi: 10.1186/s13024-017-0190-z
- 30.Alzheimer's Association. (2020). 2020 Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 16(3), 391-460.
- 31.World Health Organization. (2020). Dementia: Key Facts. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/dementia>
- 32.Livingston, G., Huntley, J., Sommerlad, A., Ames, D., Ballard, C., Banerjee, S., ... & Mukadam, N. (2020). Dementia prevention, intervention, and care: 2020 report of the Lancet Commission. *The Lancet*, 396(10248), 413-446.
- 33.(2015) Alzheimer's disease genetics fact sheet. National Institute of Aging.
- 34.Rygiel K (2016) Novel strategies for alzheimer's disease treatment: An overview of anti-amyloid beta monoclonal antibodies. *Indian J Pharmacol* 48: 629-636.
- 35.Hardy J, De Strooper B (2017) Alzheimer's disease: Where next for anti-amyloid therapies? *Brain* 140: 853-855.
- 36.Serrano-Pozo A., Frosch M.P., Masliah E., Hyman B.T. Neuropathological alterations in Alzheimer disease. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Med*. 2011;1:a006189. doi: 10.1101/cshperspect.a006189.
- 37.Spires-Jones T.L., Hyman B.T. The intersection of amyloid beta and tau at synapses in Alzheimer's disease. *Neuron*. 2014;82:756–771. doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2014.05.004.
- 38.Singh S.K., Srivastav S., Yadav A.K., Srikrishna S., Perry G. Overview of Alzheimer's disease and some therapeutic approaches targeting abeta by using several synthetic and herbal compounds. *Oxidative Med. Cell. Longev*. 2016;2016:7361613. doi: 10.1155/2016/7361613.
- 39.Cras P., Kawai M., Lowery D., Gonzalez-DeWhitt P., Greenberg B., Perry G. Senile plaque neurites in Alzheimer disease accumulate amyloid precursor protein. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*. 1991;88:7552–7556. doi: 10.1073/pnas.88.17.7552.
- 40.Perl D.P. Neuropathology of Alzheimer's disease. *Mt. Sinai J. Med. N. Y.* 2010;77:32–42. doi: 10.1002/msj.20157.
- 41.Armstrong R.A. The molecular biology of senile plaques and neurofibrillary tangles in Alzheimer's disease. *Folia Neuropathol*. 2009;47:289–299.
- 42.Chen G.F., Xu T.H., Yan Y., Zhou Y.R., Jiang Y., Melcher K., Xu H.E. Amyloid beta: Structure, biology and structure-based therapeutic development. *Acta Pharmacol. Sin*. 2017;38:1205–1235. doi: 10.1038/aps.2017.28.
- 43.Tabaton M., Piccini A. Role of water-soluble amyloid-beta in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease. *Int. J. Exp. Pathol*. 2005;86:139–145. doi: 10.1111/j.0959-9673.2005.00428.x.
- 44.Brion J.P. Neurofibrillary tangles and Alzheimer's disease. *Eur. Neurol*. 1998;40:130–

140. doi: 10.1159/000007969.
45. Metaxas A., Kempf S.J. Neurofibrillary tangles in Alzheimer's disease: Elucidation of the molecular mechanism by immunohistochemistry and tau protein phospho-proteomics. *Neural Regen. Res.* 2016;11:1579–1581. doi: 10.4103/1673-5374.193234.
46. Overk C.R., Masliah E. Pathogenesis of synaptic degeneration in Alzheimer's disease and Lewy body disease. *Biochem Pharm.* 2014;88:508–516. doi: 10.1016/j.bcp.2014.01.015.
47. Lleo A., Nunez-Llaves R., Alcolea D., Chiva C., Balateu-Panos D., Colom-Cadena M., Gomez-Giro G., Munoz L., Querol-Vilaseca M., Pegueroles J., et al. Changes in synaptic proteins precede neurodegeneration markers in preclinical Alzheimer's disease cerebrospinal fluid. *Mol. Cell. Proteom. Mcp.* 2019;18:546–560. doi: 10.1074/mcp.RA118.001290.
48. Tarawneh R., D'Angelo G., Crimmins D., Herries E., Griest T., Fagan A.M., Zipfel G.J., Ladenson J.H., Morris J.C., Holtzman D.M. Diagnostic and prognostic utility of the synaptic marker neurogranin in Alzheimer Disease. *JAMA Neurol.* 2016;73:561–571. doi: 10.1001/jamaneurol.2016.0086.
49. Hardy, J., & Selkoe, D. J. (2002). The amyloid hypothesis of Alzheimer's disease: progress and problems on the road to therapeutics. *Science*, 297(5580), 353-356.
50. Goedert, M., Spillantini, M. G., Jakes, R., Rutherford, D., & Crowther, R. A. (1989). Multiple isoforms of human microtubule-associated protein tau: sequences and localization in neurofibrillary tangles of Alzheimer's disease. *Neuron*, 3(4), 519-526.
51. Heneka, M. T., Carson, M. J., El Khoury, J., Landreth, G. E., Brosseron, F., Feinstein, D. L., ... & Kummer, M. P. (2015). Neuroinflammation in Alzheimer's disease. *The Lancet Neurology*, 14(4), 388-405.
52. Butterfield, D. A., & Halliwell, B. (2019). Oxidative stress, dysfunctional glucose metabolism and Alzheimer disease. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 20(3), 148-160.
53. Spiros-Jones, T. L., & Hyman, B. T. (2014). The intersection of amyloid beta and tau at synapses in Alzheimer's disease. *Neuron*, 82(4), 756-771.
54. Zlokovic, B. V. (2011). Neurovascular pathways to neurodegeneration in Alzheimer's disease and other disorders. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 12(12), 723-738.
55. Holtzman, D. M., Morris, J. C., & Goate, A. M. (2011). Alzheimer's disease: the challenge of the second century. *Science translational medicine*, 3(77), 77sr1-77sr1.
56. Blennow, K., Dubois, B., Fagan, A. M., Lewczuk, P., de Leon, M. J., & Hampel, H. (2015). Clinical utility of cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers in the diagnosis of early Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 11(1), 58-69.
57. McKhann, G. M., Knopman, D. S., Chertkow, H., Hyman, B. T., Jack Jr, C. R., Kawas, C. H., ... & Phelps, C. H. (2011). The diagnosis of dementia due to Alzheimer's disease: Recommendations from the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 7(3), 263-269.
58. Sperling, R. A., Aisen, P. S., Beckett, L. A., Bennett, D. A., Craft, S., Fagan, A. M., ... & Phelps, C. H. (2011). Toward defining the preclinical stages of Alzheimer's disease: Recommendations from the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 7(3), 280-292.
59. Lyketsos, C. G., Steinberg, M., Tschanz, J. T., Norton, M. C., Steffens, D. C., & Breitner, J. C. (2002). Mental and behavioral disturbances in dementia: findings from the Cache County Study on Memory in Aging. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*, 159(5), 708-714.
60. Ballard, C., O'Brien, J., James, I., Mynt, P., Lana, M. M., Potkins, D., ... & Wilcock, G. (2009). Quality of life for people with dementia living in residential and nursing home care: the impact of performance on activities of daily living, behavioral and psychological symptoms, language skills, and psychotropic drugs. *International Psychogeriatrics*, 21(2), 361-376.
61. Volicer, L., Harper, D. G., Manning, B. C., Goldstein, R., & Satlin, A. (2001). Sundowning and circadian rhythms in Alzheimer's disease. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*, 158(5), 704-711.
62. American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (5th ed.)*. Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publishing.
63. Jack, C. R. Jr., Bennett, D. A., Blennow, K., Carrillo, M. C., Dunn, B., Haeberlein, S. B., ... & NIA-AA Research Framework: Toward a Biological Definition of Alzheimer's Disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 14(4), 535-562.
64. Sperling, R. A., Aisen, P. S., Beckett, L. A., Bennett, D. A., Craft, S., Fagan, A. M., ... & Phelps, C. H. (2011). Toward defining the preclinical stages of Alzheimer's disease:

- recommendations from the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 7(3), 280-292.
65. Birks J. Cholinesterase inhibitors for Alzheimer's disease. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2006;(1):CD005593.
66. McShane R, Areosa Sastre A, Minakaran N. Memantine for dementia. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2006;(2):CD003154.
67. Livingston G, Sommerlad A, Orgeta V, et al. Dementia prevention, intervention, and care. *Lancet*. 2017;390(10113):2673-2734.
68. Cummings J, Lee G, Mordsdorf T, et al. Alzheimer's disease drug development pipeline: 2020. *Alzheimers Dement (N Y)*. 2020;6(1):e12050.
69. Rolland Y, Pillard F, Klapouszczak A, et al. Exercise program for nursing home residents with Alzheimer's disease: a 1-year randomized, controlled trial. *J. Am. Geriatr. Soc.* 2007; 55:158-65.
70. Ströhle A, Schmidt DK, Schultz F, et al. Drug and exercise treatment of Alzheimer disease and mild cognitive impairment: a systematic review and meta-analysis of effects on cognition in randomized controlled trials. *Am. J. Geriatr. Psychiatry* 2015; 23:1234-49.
71. Hoffmann K, Sobol NA, Frederiksen KS, et al. Moderate-to-high intensity physical exercise in patients with Alzheimer's disease: A randomized controlled trial. *J. Alzheimers Dis.* 2015; 50:443-53.
72. Chapman SB, Aslan S, Spence JS, et al. Shorter term aerobic exercise improves brain, cognition, and cardiovascular fitness in aging. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2013; 5:75.
73. Sacco G, Caillaud C, Ben Sadoun G, et al. Exercise plus cognitive performance over and above exercise alone in subjects with mild cognitive impairment. *J. Alzheimers Dis.* 2016; 50:19-25.
74. Forbes D, Forbes SC, Blake CM, et al. Exercise programs for people with dementia. *Cochrane Database Syst. Rev.* 2015; CD006489. DOI: 10.1002/14651858.CD006489.pub4.
75. Farina N, Rusted J, Tabet N. The effect of exercise interventions on cognitive outcome in Alzheimer's disease: a systematic review. *Int. Psychogeriatr.* 2014; 26:9-18.
76. Alzheimer's Association. (2021). Alzheimer's Disease Facts and Figures.
77. Cummings, J., et al. (2021). Alzheimer's disease drug development pipeline: 2021.
78. Brodaty, H., & Donkin, M. (2009). Family caregivers of people with dementia. *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, 11(2), 217-228.
79. Chin, A. L., Negash, S., & Hamilton, R. (2011). Diversity and disparity in dementia: The impact of ethnoracial differences in Alzheimer disease. *Alzheimer Disease & Associated Disorders*, 25(3), 187-195.
80. Livingston, G., et al. (2017). Dementia prevention, intervention, and care. *The Lancet*, 390(10113), 2673-2734.
81. Long, J. M., & Holtzman, D. M. (2019). Alzheimer Disease: An Update on Pathobiology and Treatment Strategies. *Cell*, 179(2), 312-339.
82. Ienca, M., et al. (2017). Intelligent Assistive Technology for Alzheimer's Disease and Other Dementias: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 56(4), 1301-1340.